

TIPS OF TEACHING AND IMPROVE SPEAKING SKILLS IN ENGLISH

Jalalova Sevara Janabay kizi

Bachelor degree student Chirchik State Pedagogical University

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Abstract. This article is about the useful tips of improving speaking skills in teaching and learning English. The article deals with English communication skills. Speaking is delivery of language through the mouth. To speak, we create sounds using many parts of our body, including the lungs, vocal tract, vocal chords, tongue, teeth and lips. Speaking is an oral form of verbal communication.

Keywords: the linguistic component, the psychological component, reproduction, methodological component.

СОВЕТЫ ПО ОБУЧЕНИЮ И УЛУЧШЕНИЮ РАЗГОВОРНЫХ НАВЫКОВ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. Эта статья посвящена полезным советам по улучшению разговорных навыков при преподавании и изучении английского языка. В статье рассматриваются навыки общения на английском языке. Говорение - это произнесение языка через рот. Чтобы говорить, мы создаем звуки, используя многие части нашего тела, включая легкие, голосовой тракт, голосовые связки, язык, зубы и губы. Говорение - это устная форма вербального общения.

Ключевые слова: лингвистический компонент, психологический компонент, воспроизведение, методологический компонент.

Speaking about the content of teaching speaking, it is necessary to allocate three basic components:

1) The linguistic component - is a language and speech material, providing students the opportunity to engage in dialogue in the framework of themes and learning situations.

2) The psychological component - is the mastery of the skills and habits⁷ of expressive speech. It is associated with the implementation of such operations as:

a) Reproduction – is an imitation of what he heard from the teacher.

b) the transformation or conversion related to the change of grammatical formed the statements. For example, the conversion of the first person in the 3rd person.

I live in Tashkent - He lives in Moscow.

3) Methodological component - is designed to offer students methods of teaching on the mastery of speaking English.

For example, the ability to use the legs, the ability to create their own support.

There are various reasons behind this phenomenon – some of them more obvious than others. In this article, I would like to give you a few tips to help overcome the difficulties you might be experiencing, using some of the simplest methods to improve your English communication skills.

1. Slow Down Your Speaking Speed. You might be an eloquent speaker when it comes to your mother tongue, but expecting the same standards from yourself when speaking in a foreign language may not be very realistic. Especially, if you're at the early stages of learning. Learners are often told not to worry about the mistakes they're making, however, it is easy to understand why you would like to make a good impression on your audience. In order to overcome this

difficulty, you may try slowing down your speaking speed. Nobody will hold it against you if you speak more slowly and clearly. Great speakers do the same to get their message across. Selecting your words carefully may also be seen as a sign of respect towards your audience. It shows that you want to give them the best possible answer.

2. Give Yourself Time to Think. You may be worried that the people you're talking to are impatient and would like you to say what you want as quickly as possible. First of all, it may not be true – people often prefer a well-thought-out answer to a rushed one. So just relax. Another practical thing you can do is equipping yourself with fixed phrases you can use when remaining silent doesn't seem to be an option.

Here's an example:

Why is there so much violence on TV? That's a good question. Let me think for a moment, I haven't really thought about it before. Well, I suppose...

Here the speaker gains considerable amount of time to reflect just by repeating the question and adding a few sentences. If you do the same, you'll sound more fluent and won't feel the pressure of having to say something before you're ready. Fixed or set phrases are phrases whose words are usually fixed in a certain order. They can be verb patterns, idioms, collocations – basically anything we always say in one particular way. For example:

- during the day
- in the meantime
- It's been a long time since

3. Learn Sentences. In a way, this will take the pressure off too. When you learn a new word, try to memorize a couple of sentences that contain it. There might come a time when you can use one particular sentence with little, or no alteration at all. Unfortunately, many people learn words by heart, but have no idea how to use them in a sentence. It will be such a relief not having to worry about whether the sentence is correct grammatically or not.

4. Learn to Listen. When speaking in a foreign language, you might be so focused on what you are saying and whether it's correct or not, that you forget to listen to what others are saying. This is a big mistake as they might be using the exact words or grammar you'll be needing later on. So pay attention to what's being said around you, it's your most important resource at the time of speaking to someone.

ESL students need to know speaking rules, if they want to speak fluently.

Practice Speaking what you hear! Reading, listening, and speaking are the most important aspects of any language. The same is true for English. However, speaking is the only requirement to be fluent. It is normal for babies and children to learn speaking first, become fluent, then start reading, then writing. So the natural order is listening, speaking, reading, then writing.

First Problem. Isn't it strange that schools across the world teach reading first, then writing, then listening, and finally speaking? Although it is different, the main reason is when you learn a second language, you need to read material to understand and learn it. So, even though the natural order is listening, speaking, reading, then writing, the order for ESL students is reading, listening, speaking, then writing. Second Problem. The reason many people can read and listen is because that's all they practice. But in order to speak English fluently, you need to practice speaking. Don't stop at the listening portion, and when you study, don't just listen. Speak out loud the material you are listening to and practice what you hear. Practice speaking out loud until your mouth and brain

can do it without any effort. By doing so, you will be able to speak English fluently. You are being able to speak a language is not related to how smart you are. Anyone can learn how to speak any language.

This is a proven fact by everyone in the world. Everyone can speak at least one language. Whether you are intelligent, or lacking some brain power, you are able to speak one language. This was achieved by being around that language at all times. In your country, you hear and speak your language constantly.

You will notice that many people who are good English speakers are the ones who studied in an English speaking school. They can speak English not because they went to an English speaking school, but because they had an environment where they can be around English speaking people constantly. Another problem I see is that many students study the news. However, the language they speak is more formal and the content they use is more political and not used in regular life. It is important to understand what they are saying, but this is more of an advanced lesson that should be studied after learning the fundamental basics of English.

Studying English with a friend who is not a native English speaker is both good and bad. You should be aware of the pros and cons of speaking with a non native speaking friend. Practicing with a non native person will give you practice. You can also motivate each other and point out basic mistakes. But you might pick up bad habits from one another if you are not sure about what are correct and incorrect sentences.

So use these practice times as a time period to practice the correct material you studied. Not to learn how to say a sentence. In short, study English material that you can trust, that is commonly used, and that is correct. Summing up, the English language is developing around the world. That's why, each person should learn to speak English language. It is important for human at the present. I think that to know English today is absolutely necessary for every educated man, for every good specialist. These are the rules that will help you achieve your goal of speaking English fluently.

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